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Research Article

**THE ASSOCIATION OF AN IMPACTED MANDIBULAR THIRD
MOLAR TOOTH WITH AN ONSET OF DIVERSE INFECTIONS
SUCH AS CARRIES, IRREVERSIBLE PULPITIS,
PERICORONITIS WITH RESPECT TO ANGULATION TYPE****¹Dr. Bariq Zaeem Mirza, ²Dr. Hafsa Mansoor, ³Dr. Ummara, ⁴Dr. Muhammad Sohaib
Yousaf**¹Medical Officer, Mohy ud Din Islamic Medical University Mir Pur Azad Kashmir²Madinah Teaching Hospital Faisalabad³Punjab Dental Hospital, Lahore⁴MO BHU 67ML**Abstract**

Most frequent tooth extraction is reported for an impacted mandibular third molar tooth because of multiple infections such as carries, irreversible pulpitis, pericoronitis etc. In this research, we aimed to determine infections frequency associated with an impacted mandibular third molar with respect to various angulations of the Winter's Classification in the total of one hundred patients at Services Hospital, Lahore (March to November 2017). We carried out radiographic and clinical assessments of all the patients for angulation types and infections specifically for the lower third molar and collected all the information of a designated proforma for further statistical analysis on SPSS software. In the light of research outcomes, females were dominant over males in terms of population as the female to male ratio was (2.8:1.0). The patients (52%) of (21 – 25) years of age bracket were found with mandibular third molar infections; whereas, most common infection was pericoronitis, which was reported among 49.0% patients.

In the light of Winter's classification outcomes, the majority (46%) had an impacted tooth in Mesio-angular, 8% had in Distoangular and 3% had in the classification of horizontal angulation. Most common involvement of carries was reported in the impactions of Mesio-angular classification (25%).

Keywords: *Infections, Molar, Mandibular, Angulation, Pericoronitis, Carries and Winter's Classification.*

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INTRODUCTION:

All the patients were commonly reporting for the partially infected mandibular third molar consultations at the oral surgery department of the hospital. Most frequent tooth extraction is reported for an impacted mandibular third molar tooth because of multiple infections such as carries, irreversible pulpitis, pericoronitis etc. [1, 2]. An impacted tooth refers to a tooth which is removed from the onset of eruption either partially functional or as a result of obstruction such as soft tissues, bone or tooth [3, 4]. It is frequently removed tooth because of ninety percent infections which include caries, irreversible pulpitis and pericoronitis of mandibular third molar, mandibular second molar for distal caries, pocketing, periodontal diseases, inflammatory cyst and alveolar bone loss associated to its extraction also accounting for the facial life-threatening space infections and severe infections [5 – 8].

Pericoronitis refers to peri coronal tissues inflammation around the surface of partially impacted third molar among seventy percent of the patients and accounts for the sixty percent of the vertical angulations in females having an age bracket of (16 – 30) years [9, 10]. Infections like pulpitis, caries and periapical are in the second slot of repeatedly occurring infections having an association with Distoangular and Masio-angular impactions [11]. Above ten percent impacted third molars have an involvement of deep pocketing, food packing and alveolar bone loss second or distal molar. Periodontal issues are common in seventy percent population that with an age of thirty-five years frequently presenting Mesio-angular implications [12].

Infections of periapical, pulpal and peri-coronal nature of third lower molar may also spread up to sub-mandibular, buccal, pterygomandibular, sublingual and other associated facial spaces among eleven percent of the Mesio-angular implications [13]. The radicular cyst is common among Mesio-angular and vertical implications [14]. Whereas, most repeated of all infection is the incidence of partially impacted mandibular third molar tooth angulation [10, 11].

On an average, a total of seventy patients visited the hospital's dentistry having the infection of an impacted mandibular third molars infections every month. Therefore, we aimed to determine infections frequency associated with an impacted mandibular third molar with respect to various angulations of the Winter's Classification in the total of one hundred patients at Services Hospital, Lahore (March to November 2017).

METHODOLOGY:

We used a WHO certified sample collection software in this research to select one hundred patients with an estimated impacted third molar infection as 85% [7 – 9]. In the total sample, indoor and outdoor patients were respectively 5 and 95. We included both males and females of any age group having impacted third molar infections in the research sample. We did not include any patient having developed cyst, odontogenic tumours and a fully impacted mandibular third molar tooth in the research study. We carried out radiographic and clinical assessments of all the patients for angulation types and infections specifically for the lower third molar and collected all the information of a designated proforma for further statistical analysis on SPSS software.

RESULTS:

In the light of research outcomes, females were dominant over males in terms of population as the female to male ratio was (2.8:1.0). The patients (52%) of (21 – 25) years of age bracket were found with mandibular third molar infections; whereas, most common infection was pericoronitis, which was reported among 49.0% patients (Table – I and II). In the light of Winter's classification outcomes, the majority (46%) had an impacted tooth in Mesio-angular, 8% had in Distoangular and 3% had in the classification of horizontal angulation. Most common involvement of carries was reported in the impactions of Mesio-angular classification (25%) (Table – III). A detailed outcomes analysis of age distribution, angulation types and Winter classification is given in Table – I, II and III.

Table – I: Distribution of Age

Age	Number (100)
15 to 20 Years	8
21 to 25 Years	52
26 to 30 Years	19
31 to 35 Years	11
36 to 40 Years	7
Above 40 Years	3

Table – II: Angulation Types

Type of Angulations	Number (100)
Mesio Angular	46
Disto Angular	9
Horizontal	13
Vertical	32

Table – III: Winter Classification among Various Infections

Winter Classification	Mesio Angular	Disto Angular	Horizontal Angulation	Vertical Angulation	Total
Pericoronitis	15	8	3	23	49
Caries	25	0	8	8	41
Periodontitis	3	0	1	0	4
Fascial Space Infection	3	1	1	0	5
Radicular Cyst	0	0	0	1	1
Total	46	9	13	32	100

DISCUSSION:

The field of oral surgery repeatedly faces the extraction of the third molar on regular basis in the day to day practice due to higher impaction incidences with diverse infections that include periodontal defects, pericoronitis, inflammatory cyst, caries etc. [1 – 3, 15]. Our research included one

hundred such patients selected from the OPD of the hospital including both males and females with the respective proportion of 78% and 22%. Males were dominating the research population. Same outcomes are also produced in a series conducted at the USA with a dominance of males over females with respective proportions of 57% and 43% [16].

However, females were dominant in other research series held at Nigeria, Malaysia and Pakistan with the respective proportion of 65% in each series [17 – 19]. Ahmad and Khawaja support our outcomes about the 49% prevalence of pericoronitis in their research series [3, 20]. Angulation analysis on the basis of Winter's classification shows the prevalence of third molar impaction in Mesio-angular, vertical, horizontal and Distoangular impactions with respective proportions of 46%, 32%, 13% and 9%. Various other series also present the similar proportions of the impactions [21 – 23]. Trivial variations may have an association with dietary intake and geographical location. According to Hussain, few patients of vertical and Mesio-angular impactions also impacted their third molar [24]. We reported a common onset of Mesio-angular and Pericoronitis infections with respective proportions of 15% and 23%; similarly, Leone and two other authors also reported similar outcomes [12, 25, 26]. Ekland's outcomes about the common onset of caries because of mandibular second molar did not match our research outcomes having 3.9% versus 25%, which is lower than our outcomes; whereas, Ishfaq presented similar outcomes with a ratio of (26.5%) [12]. We reported the occurrence of periodontitis as (4%); whereas, Naofumi reported the same as (8.91%) [27]. The pulpal, peri-coronal or periapical infections of lower third molars cause the infection of facial space among five percent of Mesio-angular infection. Ishfaq and Marioni respectively reported 38.8% and 49% of patients with facial space infections because of the Mesio-angular third molar [12, 28]. Vertically impacted tooth was one percent because of the infected cyst; whereas, Rohlin and Liesel reported cyst infection as two percent [15]. Werkmeister and Sphered reported 3% and 1% respective cyst infection cases [19, 29].

CONCLUSION:

Most common infections reported among patients correlates with the onset of an impacted mandibular third molar. The increasing order of various infection of the mandibular third molar includes infected cyst, facial space infections, periodontal issues, caries and pericoronitis. Caries and pericoronitis are among most repeated infections correlating with Mesio-angular impactions. An infected radicular cyst refers to a chronic infection that has an association with a vertical impacted molar.

REFERENCES:

1. Renton T, Smeeton MC, Gurk M. Factors predictive of the difficulty of mandibular third molar surgery. *Br Dent J.* 2001;190: 607-10.
2. Hussein M, Hussein T. Peri coronal impaction

- and wisdom tooth. *J Pak Dent Assoc.* 2002; 11: 113-16.
3. Leon SA, Edenfield MJ, Cohen ME. Correlation of acute pericoronitis and position of the mandibular third molar. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 2001; 62: 245-50.
4. Rakprasitkul S. Pathological changes in pericoronal tissues of unerupted third molars. *Quintessence International.* 2001; 32:633-38.
5. Naofumi O, Yoshiko A, Masakazu G, Masahiro I, Munete N, Kenichi K. Spread of odontogenic infection arising in maxillary teeth. CT assessment. *J Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol Radiol.* 2004; 98(2): 223-31.
6. Marioni G, Rindle R, Staffieri C, Marchese R, Giorgia S, Stramare R. Deep neck infection with dental origin. Analysis of 85 consecutive cases. *Dept Oral Med Oral Surg Oral Radiol* 2008; 128(2): 201-06.
7. Werkmeister R, Fillies T, Joos U, Smolka k. The relationship between lower wisdom tooth position and cyst development, deep abscess formation and mandibular angle fracture. *J Cranio and Maxillofacial Surg.* 2005; 33: 164-68.
8. Niedzielski AI, Drugaez J, Kreska J. Panoramic radiographic predictor of mandibular third molar eruptions. *Oral Surg, Oral Med, Oral Pathol, Oral Radiol, Oral Endod.* 2006; 102(2): 154-58.
9. Jawad F, Maher R. Impaction of mandibular third molars. *J of Pak Dent Assoc* 2002; 11(2): 77-80.
10. Munhoz EA, Ferreira O, Yaedu RF, Granjeiro JM. Radiographic assessment of impacted mandibular third molar sockets filled with xenogenic bone graft. *J Br Int Radiol.* 2005; 35: 371-76.
11. Nance P, White R, Offenbacher S, Phillips C, Blakey G, Huang R. Change in mandibular third molar angulation in young adults. 2006; 64(3): 424-28.
12. White RP, Offenbacher S, Blakey GH. Chronic oral inflammation and progression of periodontal pathology in the third molar region. *J Oral and Maxillofacial Surg* 2006; 64: 880-85.
13. Eklund SA, Pittman JL. 3rd molar in insured population. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 2001; 132: 469-75.
14. Ishfaq M, Rahim A, Wahid A, Munim A. Odontogenic infections with an impacted mandibular third molar. *JPDA.* 2007;16(2): 71-76.
15. Bataineh AB. The predisposing factors of pericoronitis of the mandibular third molar in the lower jaw in Jordanian patients. *Aus Dent J.* 2003; 34(3): 227-31.

16. Haq ZU. A survey of reasons for the surgical removal of the impacted mandibular third molar in Armed Forces personnel at AFID. *Pak Oral Dent J.* 2002; 22(2): 137-139.
17. Obiecha AE, Arotiba JT, Fesolo AO. Evaluation of symptoms and patterns of mandibular third molars impactions in Nigerians. *Odontosomal Trop* 2001; 24: 22-25.
18. Bui CH, Seldin EB, Dodson TB. Types, frequencies, and risk factors for complications after third molar extraction. *J Oral Maxillofacial Surg.* 2003; 61: 1379-1389.
19. Khan A, Khitab U, Khan MT. Impacted mandibular third molars: Pattern of presentation and post-operative complications. *Pak Oral Dent J* 2010; 30: 307-12.
20. Shepherd JP, Brickley M, Jaffar RO, Tin MM. Impacted mandibular third molars among patients attending Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia. *Archives of Orofacial Sciences* 2009;4: 7-12.
21. Obiechina AE, Arotiba JT, Fasola AO. Third molar impaction, evaluation of the symptoms and pattern of impaction of mandibular third molar teeth in Nigerians. *Odontostomatol Trop* 2001; 24(93): 22-25.
22. Ahmed A, Mohamed F, Hattab K. Surgical extraction of impacted mandibular third molars: Post-operative complications and their risk factors, *JMJ* 2009; 9(4): 272-75.
23. Blondeau F, Danial NG. Extraction of the third molar. postoperative complication and their risk factor. *J Can Dent Assoc.* 2007; 73:325-32.
24. Chye CH, Sing B. Rapid cystic development in relation to impacted third molar. A case report. *Ann Acad Med.* 2005; 34:103-06.
25. Adeyemo WL. Do pathologies associated with impacted lower third molars justify prophylactic removal? A critical review of the literature of Oral Surgery oral med oral Pathol Oral Radiol Endod. 2006; 102(4): 448-52.
26. Adeyemo WL, Landiende AL, Ogunlewe OM. Prophylactic surgical removal of the impacted third molar. *Pak Oral Dent J.* 2005;25(1): 11-14.
27. Khawaja AN. Third molar impaction. A review. *Pak Oral Dent J.* 2006; 15(2): 97-101.
28. Peterson LJ, Ellis E, Hupp JR, Tucker MR. Principles of management of impacted teeth in Contemporary oral and maxillofacial surgery. 4th Ed 2003; 9: 184-213.
29. Paolo B, Maria C. Submandibular space infection: potentially lethal infection: *J Oral Maxillofacial Surg.* 2009; 13(3): 327-33.